

Information Communication Technology (ICT) as a Veritable Tool for Information Management in Judicial Libraries in Nigeria

Envuluanza Magaji Agu
National Judicial Institutes, Abuja

Abstract:- This study explored the usefulness of information communication technology (ICT) toward achieving effective service delivery to enhance the administration of justice among the citizenry. The study surveyed the opinions of writers on the subject matter after which, a conclusion was drawn as a standing point of the writer. Considering the importance of libraries in information management for effective patronage, it was found that information communication technology is the only tool that ensures complete access to the world of information without considering cost, time, and border. Library services such as cataloging, classification, online public catalog, selective dissemination of information, and many other services can be achieved effectively. However, it was found that most of the efforts made toward using ICT in Nigerian Libraries collapses owing to certain factors. Given the above, strategies emanating from how to provide adequate funding, create awareness or orientation of library staff toward ICT, a provision of inadequate training to both library staff and clientele must be considered as necessary to ensure the application of ICT for library management for effective justice administration.

Keywords: Information communication technology, Information management, and justice Libraries

I. INTRODUCTION

The rapid progress in ICT has significantly changed the scope of the function of the library. Such swift improvements led to the introduction of new libraries and forms of services. New ideas have arisen in the development of electronic collections, such as the digital collection and the virtual library. There have been improvements in library research worldwide and poorly developed countries are no exception. As they progress in ICT has significantly affected the scope of the library's task, poorly developed libraries live to regret their inability to partake in the global information management changes. Such rapid changes have led to the introduction of new libraries and specialized services (Seyed and Tajafari, 2012).

Information Communication Technology (ICT) can be defined as the use of any computer and the Internet to make data and information services accessible to the user community or library patrons. The word is widely used to discuss a variety of techniques, including ICT devices. The ICT application is used to handle one or more library routine operations, such as acquiring, serial monitoring, cataloging and classification, and the OPAC. This includes the concept

of using data handling, storage, processing, and dissemination techniques in general. ICT can also be seen as an information communication facility and element for contemporary computing (Ebunuwele, Ola, & Uduebor, 2014). They also point out that this term covers all IT, network components, and application software for digital world connection. In agreement with other scholars, Rouse also noted that this term encompasses both information technology, networking components, and application software, and facilitates interactive connectivity.

Information and communication technology (ICT) administration in legal libraries is a very important responsibility that both attorneys and librarians in law libraries must prioritize. Finding appropriate legislation to address legal questions is, in essence, the goal of legal study. Finding or recognizing the laws that control how people behave in society is what it means to do legal research. For attorneys to succeed in their profession, a solid grasp of research expertise is a need. Lawyers need to be proficient in legal research since they are frequently asked to provide legal advice or solve legal issues, which necessitates understanding the rules that apply to certain issues and where to find them (Simeon, Eseoho, & Ehikioya, 2014).

When a client wants legal representation to seek relief from a difficult circumstance or possibly files a court case on a certain outcome, the attorney may need to research to determine the applicable laws. A lawyer could be required to advise a client on a new business venture, such as registering a business name, signing a contract, or purchasing real estate, and to do so effectively, the lawyer must be aware of the customer's rights and obligations as they are outlined under the law. But the law library offers materials and aid for research that are germane to the questions that attorneys are asking in their study. There are several sources of legal regulations in law libraries.

The Nigerian legal system In the opinion of Beredugo (2009) refers to the entirety of the law or legal rules and the legal machinery, which cover the constitution, political structure, government, legislature, the judiciary, the justice delivery system, the administrative agencies, and even the legal profession that are present in the country. The Nigerian legal system also takes into account the historical perspective of the transformational legal form that emerged from a pre-legal society to a plural legal system with undertones of various distinct systems of law, including the native customary law, received English law, and local or municipal legislation.

It is essential to consider pre-colonial, colonial, and post-colonial legal transformations to comprehend Nigeria's legal system. But before colonialism, the ethnic groups that subsequently came to constitute Nigeria followed native or customary rules that were employed to control society's behavior and manage the affairs of the populace. By the time Nigeria was a British colony, the English legal system had been imported to the nation and included colonial statutes, common law, and equity principles. The Nigerian legal system doubled with the addition of this and the antecedent system of customary law. Additionally, Nigeria (acquired) the English legal system when it gained independence from Britain in 1960. The post-colonial government did not have to settle for only one legal system. A national legal system that is based on Nigerian principles of law and justice has evolved, according to Beredugo (2009), through local legislative enactments and case law.

The legal profession requires information on how to decide a case, argue or represent a client in court, and how pass the bar test. As a result, the law library is just as crucial to the legal profession as the legal profession itself (Olorunfemi and Mostert, 2012). Because the value of the legal advice and opinions offered is based on an understanding of the sources and requirements of the law, research in law libraries is dynamic and interesting. Law libraries, in the opinion of Abubakar (2005), serve as a laboratory for the legal profession and are much more concerned with current information, its accessibility, operation, preservation, dissemination, analysis, and synthesis, all of which have a lot to offer the legal profession in the conduct of research. The essence of existence of any legal library according to Abubakar (2005) is to maximize the accessibility of its contents to suit the needs of its users.

The law library is extremely important in all facets of the legal profession; maintaining a setting that is favorable to study, stimulates academic inquiry (The university of Iowa, 2019)

A law library offers its clients a wide range of services. In light of the goal of this study, emphasis should be placed on the research services offered by law libraries in addition to their standard offerings. After examining the Nigerian legal system, the sources of law, and various library information resources, it is necessary to describe the fundamental research services provided by a law library. The legal library will assist users in locating the information they need by assisting in the selection of the appropriate sources based on their needs, resources, and location, according to Cornell University Law School (2019). As implied by the general rule, research librarians do not, however, conduct users' research or provide legal advice; rather, they only assist researchers by making available the information resources they require to support their research activities.

Judicial libraries are libraries that are typically found on a court's grounds, according to Anaeme (2015). In other terms, they're frequently called court libraries. They were created to assist the judicial branch of the government. They

assist judges, magistrates, and working attorneys in the case preparation and administration of justice. The Supreme Court Library in Abuja, the Court of Appeal Libraries—including the Sharia Court of Appeal in the Federal Capital Territory and the States, the Federal and State High Court Law Libraries, the National Industrial Court libraries, and Magistrate Court libraries located all over the nation are among them. The primary purpose of libraries is to support the courts' ability to administer justice quickly and effectively by acquiring and making available foundational legal resources in print and digital formats for research. Legal libraries are suppose to be stocked with fundamental resources like those that are specified under library holdings.

II. THE OBJECTIVE OF THE STUDY

The need o elaborate on the usefulness of ICT owing to the consequence of the flow of information and expertise in a variety of contexts and areas of specialization particularly, in justice libraries, is very crucial for efficient library service provision. The purpose of this study is to expand on the effectiveness of ICT in discharging various library operations to improve service quality to ensure the freedom of citizens. It also tried to highlight the usefulness of ICT and strategies for productive use of the technology.

Information resources have grown in importance to persons in a variety of professions in the twenty-first century. Judges, attorneys, and law students all need the information to carry out their daily duties in the legal profession. This is because the law is a highly specialized and technical subject, making it the domain of a professional group of practitioners. This field requires knowledge of how judges decide cases, lawyers present cases or represent clients in court, and how to pass the bar exam (Olorunfemi & Mostert, 2012).

Information resources are an essential tool needed for the day-to-day operations of those in the legal profession. These individuals require legal information to make critical choices that could directly affect human life. Making wise selection is highly likely if the legal information resources retrieved is reliable. Conversely,, making wise decisions becomes more difficult if the information is unreliable. Better information therefore typically results in better decisions (Walonick, 2004). Judiciary libraries, therefore, keep a variety of informational items about legal matters, which call for specialized knowledge to manage; particularly court decisions, legislative enactments, constitutions, treaties, ordinances, and administrative rules and regulations.

The most recent technology used in libraries that are electronically operated with the use of computer network operations and services is digital communications technology. The current issue with creating, encoding, conserving, accessing, and spreading information in libraries revolves upon pressing a button to get to the knowledge you prefer. Ironically, there are three types of IT systems that can be utilized as libraries: systems, storage devices, and telephones. A machine with mathematical control technology is used to carry out tasks, such as in the sectors

of information management and libraries. Due to the central processing unit's (CPU) limited data space, additional storage devices including magnetic disk and tape, as well as audiotape, are needed. Due to their ease of use, disks are the most widely utilized auxiliary storage device that is used to store information in all forms necessary. Telecommunications is another ICT application that is used in libraries and serves the purpose of transmitting or communicating information or signals on a global scale. Staff members in libraries can accomplish the following tasks with ICT:

III. RESOURCES FOR INFORMATION ACQUISITION

ICT has increased the number of publisher catalogs available for libraries to choose from. Since the services of the store or vendors were eliminated, this has initially decreased the cost of the materials. It reassures libraries that whatever title they choose will be available because distance and geography are not obstacles. Through the online method, it is now able to provide feedback, ask questions, request the purchase of library materials, and make payments without leaving the office. Even more than a physical link or engagement, it has made it feasible to speak with publishers and merchants on their websites to conduct business.

A. *The use of Electronic Cataloguing*

A library's thorough classification, cataloging, and organization of the subject matter and heights or sizes according to the subject are what set them apart from a bookshop. The necessity of making sure that resources are correctly cataloged and categorized to use them effectively and efficiently was the reason librarians were made more aware of the issue. Currently, ICT enables remote libraries to access the massive repositories of the larger libraries in developing countries to accept or modify their bibliographic data for their library use. Electronic catalogs have also changed the environment for cataloging and classification (Adeleke and Olorunsola, 2010).

B. *Online Classification of Information Resources:*

In the past, librarians struggled with issues including maintaining a single version of the categorization scheme, choosing which classification scheme to employ, and determining what kind of library to utilize such classification in. the library. As ICT advances, a growing number of online records are made available, allowing for the copying of class marks from books with the same title and author. opening a book from page to page to determine if the material is no longer relevant is a difficult task. The British Library catalog, Australia's Trove-National Library catalog, and the Library of Congress electronic index are three prominent examples of these online catalogs. Since records and copies of those databases are always available to libraries for cataloging their books and materials, they can be searched online, leading to the creation of a single catalog and that has helped in actualizing global resources sharing.

C. *Online Public Access Catalogue (OPAC).*

An improved method of leveraging ICT to access information services and their locations through the internet service is the online public access catalog (OPAC). ICT via OPAC enables users to access stocks of numerous library collections as opposed to using a single library's catalog cabinet. As a result, maintaining a library collection is less expensive, pen and paper waste has been eliminated, and catalog can now be planned. It is believed that it is the quickest way to get information on the library's collection, weekly visitors, and other recent acquisitions.

D. *Global Online Library*

A computer and computer network form the backbone of a digital library because they are required for processing reading material into digital form. Without a computer, even published books cannot be converted to digital form. Digital libraries contain all available reading material, including PDF, HTML, audio, video, and services. Furthermore, relying on the computer and network Most scholars these days choose to avoid librarians who are unable to provide such amenities and services in their libraries. For the library staff to be current and useful, this component necessitates the development of more ICT literacy.

E. *Resource Sharing Through Union Catalog:*

According to a well-known proverb, giving the appropriate information to the right user at the right time is what separates the rich from the poor. ICT has made it possible for resource sharing amongst automated and networked libraries and information centers around the world. It offers a fantastic opportunity for a library to collaborate with other libraries to share its resources, both material and human. Technology plays a significant role in cooperative personnel training, cooperative personnel acquisition, cooperative processing (cataloging and classification), exchange of information materials (e-resources), joint publications, networking, and staff exchange for seminars and workshops (Igwe, 2010).

F. *Use of Library Automation Software:*

The issue of automation, which has removed human involvement from library services, is one of the best ICT activities in information resource control. The general goal of modern automation technology is to offer the most services for the least amount of money and time. The use of ICTs in libraries to carry out library operations and services to improve the quality of services provided to the user community is known as library automation. Libraries are free to choose and employ any of the numerous library automation programs like TINLIB, Koha, etc. that are available for use in library operations. The software's purpose is to automate the library's processes for stock verification, serials management, acquisition, cataloging, and circulation. ICT is employed in many library housekeeping operations as well as for different library activities.

G. Radio Frequency Identification

The days of keeping track of borrowers' lending and receiving activities in the library using registers are long gone thanks to radio frequency identification. This new technology has altered how library transactions are conducted (check-in and check-out). Libraries offer ICT-based library services to broaden the range of options for quick and user-friendly services. The "Radio Frequency Identification" technology is one of the best innovations for libraries. To offer a more enriched and effective library service, libraries are now implementing this technology. Offering rapid and efficient services to the anxious information seeker is intended to save consumers' time.

H. Circuit-Switched Television

One of the biggest contributions made by ICT to the security issue is the installation of a special camera in a secret spot that will capture all actions taking place in the library. With the use of this tool, libraries may monitor employees who skip work or aren't performing their tasks properly without the need for supervisors. The problem of theft and mutilation in libraries have also been resolved, using the. CCTV is more affordable when comparing the upkeep costs of the technology and the degree of accuracy in reporting the evidence that was present.

In addition to the aforementioned, the use of interactive social media technology to deliver library services has improved the effectiveness of those services. The web-based and mobile social media tools can be utilized to transform communication into a participatory dialog.

I. Noter-Up Service:

This service involves updating previously passed laws whenever new laws are passed. The alteration is noticed, typed out, and put on the proper page in the law book to carry out noter-up services. Additionally, Honourable Judges are need to be supplied copies of the revision or changes, and other library users are informed of the changes. This will undoubtedly serve as a guide for them as they administer justice and help them avoid mistakes.

J. Email communication:

Library use library may send resources and queries to the librarian via email, and the librarian will respond to them via email. It eliminates the issue of physically locating the materials. The only issue with this medium is that it eliminates the values gained from face-to-face interactions and social interactions with other library users.

K. Diverse Electronic Discussion Forum:

An online forum, like Facebook Zoom and many other social media platforms that were established for remote message transmission, allows users to ask questions and express opinions. These platforms were particularly successful in 2020 during COVID 19.

L. Legal Data Bases

To access legal resources, many law libraries throughout the world are now using online legal databases. The two most popular ones are WESTLAW and LexisNexis. Large amounts of information and research are stored in databases that are used by researchers, law students, and attorneys in practice.

M. Law Blogs

A blog, which is short for "weblog," is a website that is composed of postings that are organized chronologically and by date and category. Blawgs are blogs about the law. Blogs have developed into helpful updating tools for a range of legal specializations, keeping lawyers promptly informed of changes and problems in their fields of expertise. Blogs have attained a certain status, appearing in court documents, and Collaborative encyclopedia: The best illustration of a collaborative encyclopedia that anybody may freely edit and add to is Wikipedia. Wiki technology is the foundation of it. One of the most popular websites in the world is Wikipedia.

N. Simple Syndication (RSS):

Developed by Netscape in 1999, this syndication style has been immensely popular for gathering updates to blogs and news websites. Because the user receives just pertinent content, receives notifications when new content is available and is not required to learn new technologies, RSS offers an alternate distribution platform. The user can choose automatically which RSS feeds from the millions of blogs, new services, and content providers they want to subscribe.

O. Strategies For The Effective Provision And Upkeep Of ICT For The Management Of Judicial Libraries.

After taking into account the value and requirement of information communication technology for the efficient management of amusing libraries, it is essential to assure the application of the following strategies:

- a) Provision of Proper ICT Training for Library Staff
Since the appeal for ICT experts in Nigeria to support the development and growth of ICT by lowering the price of installation of ICT equipment in university libraries is not bearing fruit, vigorous training should be provided to library employees. The knowledgeable library personnel should receive sufficient ICT management and implementation support for this reason to encourage and motivate them to develop all the necessary skills to reduce installation and maintenance costs. This would not only lessen the challenges of finding technicians quickly and at steep discounts.
- b) Efforts to Raise Money for Library Support in Addition to the Annual Allocation
State governments and alumni should join together to help the libraries in their respective states. To make sure that education is well-cared for, states have made this one of their goals or priorities. Additionally, by supporting libraries in the area, it will free the library from its financial burdens and enable it to offer the community greater services.

c) Proper Provision of ICT Orientation for Library Staff and Patrons

The need for employing ICT and its benefits over traditional library operations should be better understood by library staff and patrons. To put it another way, if library employees are fully aware of the value of ICT in carrying out their responsibilities, they have had the honor of endorsing it and are aware that it will only require a small amount of effort to conduct their daily services. The justification is those good intentions are affected by ignorance.

d) Provision of Improved and Strengthened ICT Policies for Library Management

Nigerian public libraries must rigorously abide by the guidelines for implementing ICT for the benefit of the country. This will not only boost and support the education sector but also other projects and sectors that will contribute to Nigeria's socio-economic growth. The National Information and Communication Technology (ICT) Final draft policy of 2012 should be viewed by government organizations such as national, state, university, and other libraries as a call to stakeholders to consistently enforce their libraries' action plans.

IV. RECOMMENDATIONS AND CONCLUSION

In actuality, it is difficult to imagine a modern world without computer technology. The entire program is made up of how easily ICTs are accessible to judges and lawyers, computer professionals, and organizations. With the aid of ICT, delivering services to recipients has become relatively quick and straightforward, and it has also saved time for both the user and the manager. The idea of having a library with a well-stocked information resource is starting to become a thing of the past since accessing them cannot be guaranteed. With ICT today, Information centers and allied organizations are now utilizing ICT to carry out both administrative tasks and to keep providing services to information searchers.

The adoption of ICT has increased the value of facilities and information centers because librarians are using them more frequently. Information centers are moving closer to achieving their goal of providing precise, thorough, and quick data to those who need it, unlike the ICT. Before implementing any particular service, library specialists must look into the user enrollment to understand the users' information needs and the data that their conduct necessitates. The findings of this kind of research would give the library professional some direction for future work. Knowledge managers must stay current on global trends and advances in a variety of sectors, including the industry as a whole as well as all related fields. In summary, we may still conclude that the use of ICT in information centers will enable specialists to accomplish libraries' key aims, which are to deliver the right information to the right user at the right time in the right format. This is more important in justice matters since it paves the way toward ensuring freedom for the citizens when the right information is

provided to the right user and at the right time. However, the inability to provide adequate funding, proper training of library staff, and proper orientation on the usefulness to the user community make ICT application for library management a mirage.

REFERENCES

- [1.] Abubakar, I.A. (2005). Law Librarianship in the 21st Century: Professional Skills and Competencies. *Nigerian Current Legal Problems*, 6 (1), 81 -100 %207.pdf (March 20, 2019)\
- [2.] Adegboire, A.M. (2010). "Automation in two Nigerian university libraries". *Library Philosophy and Practice (e-journal)*. Paper 425.,<http://digitalcommons.unl.edu/libphilprac/425>.
- [3.] Anaeme, F. O. (2015). Strengthening the Nigerian Judicial Libraries: A call for Standards. A paper delivered at the National Workshop for Judicial Librarians, 27th -31st July 2015, Organized by the National Judicial Institute, Abuja.
- [4.] Cornell University Law School (2019). Research. [Online] Available <https://law.library.cornell.edu/research> (March 21, 2013)
- [5.] developing country: a literature review. [Online] Available <http://www.lis.uzulu.ac.za/>
- [6.] Ebuwewe, E. G., Ola, O. S., & Uduebor, E. A. (2014). Application of Information Communication Technology in academic libraries in Nigeria. *International Journal of Education and Research*, 2(12), 423-425 *Electronic Library*, 33(3), 502-523. Retrieved
- [7.] Eseho, G. E., Simeon, O. O., & Ehikioya, A. U. (2014). Application of Information Communication Technology in academic libraries in Nigeria: *International Journal of Education and Research*; 2(12); 423-436. Accessed on 3/6/2019 from: <https://www.ijern.com/journal/2014/December-2014/36>
- [8.] Igwe, K. N. (2010). Resource Sharing in the ICT Era: The Case of Nigerian University Libraries. *Journal of Interlibrary Loan, Document Delivery & Electronic Reserve*, 20(3), 173–187. <https://doi.org/10.1080/1072303X.2010.491016>
- [9.] Olorufemi, D.Y. and Mostert, J. (2012). Information-seeking behavior of law students in a
- [10.] Research/2012/Yemisi%20and%50Mostert%20SECS AL.%20UZ
- [11.] Seyed, M. T., & Tajafari, M. (2012, March). Impact of information and communication technology (ICT) on library staff training: A comparative study. *Annals of Library and Information Studies*, 59, 7-15
- [12.] The university of Iowa (2019). Law Library: Policies. [Online] Available <https://library.law.uiowa.edu/policies#Legal%20Research%20and%20Legal%20Advice>
- [13.] Walonick, D. S. (1997-2010). *A selection from survival statistics: Designing and using questionnaires*. Retrieved August 19, 2011, from <http://statpac.com>.